

EVALUATION OF THE GAINS OBTAINED THROUGH THE OLIVE PROJECT (WOMEN FARMERS MEET AGRICULTURAL INNOVATIONS-2022) SURVEY STUDY AND DATA ANALYSIS

ZEYTİN PROJESİ İLE (KADIN ÇİFTÇİLER TARIMSAL YENİLİKLERLE BULUŞUYOR-2022) ANKET ÇALIŞMASI VE VERİ ANALİZİ İLE ELDE EDİLEN KAZANIMLARIN DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ

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ABSTRACT

Olive growing is done in all regions of Türkiye except Eastern Anatolia and Central Anatolia Regions. Even if not everyone in the Marmara, Aegean and Mediterranean regions, which are located in the temperate climate zone, has an olive garden, there is definitely one olive tree in the houses that have a garden. Olive oil is also an indispensable element of Turkish cuisine. Çanakkale province stands out in terms of agriculture, as well as its historical and cultural values, ecological factors, education, culture and tourism features. Çanakkale region is also important due to its production share in Türkiye's olive cultivation, newly established olive gardens, high productivity and the quality of the local olive oils. For all these reasons, there is a need to reconsider the cultivation of olives in the region, in order to obtain higher and higher quality products from olive cultivation in Çanakkale province and to include farmer women in the process. Within the scope of the 2022 Women Farmers Meet with Agricultural Innovations Projects of the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry - Education and Publication Department, the "Dissemination of Modern Olive Cultivation Techniques in Women Farmers" project, carried out jointly with Çanakkale Provincial Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry and İzmir Bornova Olive Research Institute, was carried out in 2 stages. The project was carried out during 2021 and 2022. Institute experts provided training to women farmers in order to announce new techniques in olive cultivation, ensure the use of these techniques and improve product quality, and had them perform applications (demonstrations) in field conditions. In the meeting organized by both organizations in September, when the project started, a farmer meeting was held with female olive producers in the region about modern cultivation practices, and "preliminary survey" study was conducted before the trainings. With this project, it was aimed to increase the awareness of women farmers and to ensure that they use modern production techniques with an innovative approach instead of traditional methods, and trainings were organized on this subject. After the trainings, the effectiveness of the training was evaluated with the "final survey" through surveys conducted with the producers in May. As a result, it is planned to encourage more profitable olive cultivation by evaluating the adoption of modern innovative techniques at the producer level, quality production, increasing efficiency, reducing production costs, increase in income levels, and their effects on the social structure. In this article, these survey studies and the gains they brought will be examined in detail.

Keywords: Agricultural Education, Data Analysis, Olive, Survey, Türkiye- Çanakkale, Women Farmers.

ÖZET

Zeytincilik, Türkiye'de Doğu Anadolu ve İç Anadolu Bölgeleri dışındaki tüm bölgelerde yapılır. Ilıman iklim kuşağında yer alan Marmara, Ege ve Akdeniz bölgelerinde herkesin bir zeytin bahçesi olmasa bile bahçesi olan evlerde mutlaka bir tane zeytin ağacı vardır. Zeytinyağı da Türk mutfağının vazgeçilmez bir unsurudur. Çanakkale ili sahip olduğu tarihi ve kültürel değerleri, ekolojik faktörleri, eğitim, kültür ve turizm özellikleri olmakla birlikte tarımsal açıdan da ön plana çıkmaktadır. Çanakkale yöresi ayrıca Türkiye zeytinciliğindeki üretim payı, yeni tesis edilen zeytin bahçeleri, verim yüksekliği ve yöre zeytinyağlarının kaliteli olmasından dolayı önem arz etmektedir. Tüm bu nedenlerle Çanakkale ilinde yapılan zeytincilikten daha yüksek ve kalitede ürün alınması ve çiftçi kadınların sürece dâhil edilmesi ile birlikte, bölgede yapılan yetiştiriciliğin yeniden gözden geçirilmesine ihtiyaç duyulmaktadır. T.C Tarım Ve Orman Bakanlığı- Eğitim ve Yayın Dairesi Başkanlığının "2022 Yılı Kadın Çiftçiler Tarımsal Yenilikler İle Buluşuyor" Projeleri kapsamında Çanakkale İl Tarım ve Orman Müdürlüğü ve İzmir Bornova Zeytincilik Araştırma Enstitüsü ile ortaklaşa yürütülen "Kadın Çiftçilerde Modern Zeytincilikte Yetiştirme Tekniklerinin Yaygınlaştırılması" projesi 2 aşamada gerçekleştirilmiştir. Proje 2021 ve 2022 yılları boyunca gerçekleştirilmiştir. Kadın çiftçilere zeytin yetiştiriciliğinde yeni tekniklerin duyurulması, bu tekniklerin kullanımının sağlanması ve ürün kalitesinin iyileştirilmesi yönünde enstitü uzmanları eğitimler vermişler, arazi koşullarında uygulamalar (demonstrasyon) yaptırılmışlardır. Projenin başladığı Eylül ayında her 2 kuruluşun da beraber düzenlediği toplantıda bölgedeki zeytin üreticisi kadın çiftçiler ile modern yetiştiricilik uygulamaları hakkında bir çiftçi toplantısı düzenlenmiş ve eğitimler öncesi bir "Ön anket" çalışması yapılmıştır. Hayata geçirilen bu projeye kadın çiftçilerin bilinç düzeyinin artırılması ve geleneksel yöntemler yerine inovatif bir yaklaşımla modern üretim tekniklerini kullanmalarının sağlanması amaçlanmıştır ve bu konuyla ilgili eğitimler düzenlenmiştir. Eğitimler sonrası Mayıs ayında üreticilerle yapılan anket çalışmaları ile eğitimin etkinliği "son anket" ile değerlendirilmiştir. Sonuç olarak modern yenilikçi tekniklerin üretici düzeyindeki benimsenme durumu, kaliteli üretim, verimi artırma, üretim maliyetlerini düşürme, gelir seviyelerindeki artış, sosyal yapıdaki etkileri değerlendirilerek, daha rantabl hale gelen zeytin yetiştiriciliğinin teşvik edilmesi planlanmıştır. Bu makalede bu anket çalışmaları ve getirdiği kazanımlar detaylı olarak irdelenecektir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Anket, Kadın Çiftçiler, Tarımsal Eğitim, Türkiye-Çanakkale, Veri Analizi, Zeytin.

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INTRODUCTION

It is an undeniable fact that women have a strong influence in society, often in the background, in every field. It is known that although they contribute to every stage of production in both urban and rural life, they are often paid less than men. It can be said that one of the most important reasons for this is that women, especially those living in rural areas, benefit less from educational opportunities. Education is the most important factor affecting women's social position and employment opportunities. Factors that hinder women's advancement are closely related to educational, political, economic, social, cultural, legal and religious conditions. These factors lead to the emergence of inequality, injustice and exploitative conditions for women in the family, society, national, regional and international levels (Özlen and Hatun, 2024).

Nearly half of the employment in the agricultural sector is made up of women. The importance of women is increasing in the quantitative and qualitative development of agricultural production. Empowering women in the agricultural field will make a great contribution to the agricultural field and the economy. For this purpose, training activities for women farmers increase their knowledge and awareness, enabling them to be more active in the agricultural production and marketing process. Training activities for women farmers are important in terms of women participating in the decision-making process in the agricultural field and gaining decision-making and implementation skills (Fidan et al., 2017).

In the olive sector, which is one of the important branches of agricultural production, women play an important role in olive production, from planting saplings to harvest. Especially in small family businesses, post-harvest table olive processing is mostly carried out by women producers.

MATERIAL AND METOD

The main material of the study consists of data obtained through face-to-face interviews with a total of 58 female producers who participated in the training held in Çanakkale province, Pıtlıreli (26), Geyikli (17) and Dümrek (15) districts. Women producers participating in the training were given information about the cultural processes applied in olive cultivation (pruning, irrigation, spraying, fertilization, harvesting, etc.), table olive production and storage techniques, olive oil storage techniques, eco-tourism and gastronomy tourism. A survey was conducted with female producers before and after the training to reveal the change in their knowledge levels.

The secondary source data used in the research consists of data obtained from written sources related to similar studies conducted on this subject.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It was determined that approximately 32% of the producers participating in the study were between the ages of 36-45 and 21.1% were between the ages of 46-55. It is seen that the rate of female producers in the 18-25 age range is very low (5.3%). It was determined that 89.5% of the producers participating in the study were married and approximately 58% were primary school graduates. It is seen that the university graduation rate is 13.2%. 71.1% of 38 female producers stated that they were not engaged in any non-agricultural work. Female producers participating in the study are actively involved not only in olive production but also in other agricultural products from the production stage to the market and contribute significantly to family income. Despite this, it was determined that approximately 58% of the female producers participating in the study defined themselves as housewives (Table 1).

Table 1. Socio-Economic Characteristics

Age	%	Marital status	%	Education	%	Non-agricultural activity	%	Job	%
18-25	5.3	Married	89.5	Illiterate	2.6	Yes	28.9	Government official	2.6
26-35	13.2	Single	10.5	Literate	7.9	No	71.1	Farmer	28.9
36-45	31.6			Primary school	57.9			Worker	2.6
46-55	21.1			Middle school	10.5			Retired	7.9
56-60	7.9			High school	7.9			Housewife	57.9
60+	21.1			University	13.2				
Total	100		100		100		100		100

It was determined that 23.7% of the female producers participating in the study had 1-5 decares of olive land, while 13.2% did not have any olive land. In face-to-face interviews, they stated that producers who do not have olive land either produce olives by renting or contribute as labor during the olive production phase. Approximately 40% of female producers stated that their trees were between 31-45 years old. Table 2 shows that the rate of female producers who consider increasing the number of trees is approximately 61%.

Table 2. Total Land and Olive Land Assets

Olive land (%)		Tree age (%)		Would farmer consider increasing the number of trees?	
Absent	13.2	Absent	13.2	Yes	60.5
1-5 da	23.7	-15	10.5	No	39.5
6-10 da	13.2	16-30	18.4		
11-15 da	5.3	31-45	39.5		
16-20 da	10.5	45-	18.4		
20+	34.2				

As in many branches of agricultural activity, ancestral knowledge is often used when cultural processes are carried out in olive production.

Questions were asked to the producers who participated in the training about their attitudes towards practices in olive production. While 71% answered yes to the question "Does irrigation have an effect on yield and processing?" before starting the training, it was observed that approximately 95% answered yes after the training.

It is seen that approximately 24% of them have knowledge about irrigation and 76.3% do not have knowledge about it. After being informed about irrigation, approximately 68% stated that they had sufficient knowledge about irrigation, while 31.6% stated that they still did not have sufficient knowledge about irrigation.

When asked whether pesticides had an effect on olive yield and acidity, it was determined that before the training, 68.4% thought it was effective and 31.6% thought it had no effect. It is seen that after the training, the rate of those who think that spraying has an effect on yield and acidity increased to 92%. While the rate of those who had sufficient knowledge about pesticides before the training was approximately 18%, it was found to be 68.4% after the training.

While the rate of those who think that fertilization has an effect on productivity was 92% before the training, it is 100% after the training. Female producers who attended the training were asked whether they had sufficient knowledge about fertilization. While the rate of those who said they had sufficient knowledge before the training was approximately 32%, it was determined that this rate increased to 71% after the training.

While approximately 32% of those who attended the training stated that they had knowledge about fertilization in olives, it was observed that this rate increased to 71.1% after the training.

In the training given to female farmers, it was determined that while the rate of those who had sufficient knowledge about pruning before the training was approximately 26%, the rate of those who had sufficient knowledge about pruning after the training increased to 68.4%. While the rate of those who think that it is necessary to have soil and leaf analysis in olive production before the training is approximately 87%, it is seen that all female producers who attended the training after the training stated that soil and leaf analysis should be done (Table 3).

Table 3. Status of Knowledge About Practices for Olive Production

Applications for olive production	Before Education		After Education	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Does irrigation have an effect on yield?	71.1	28.9	94.7	5.3
Is there enough information about irrigation?	23.7	76.3	68.4	31.6
Does spraying have an effect on yield and acidity?	68.4	31.6	92.1	7.9
Do you have sufficient knowledge about pesticide application?	18.4	81.6	68.4	31.6
Does fertilization have an effect on yield?	92.1	7.9	100	0.0
Is there enough information about fertilization?	31.6	68.4	71.1	28.9
Is there enough information about pruning?	26.3	73.7	68.4	31.6
Effect of soil and leaf analysis on yield?	86.8	13.2	100	0.0

In the training given to women producers in Çanakkale districts, information was given about gastronomy tourism, ecotourism and cooperatives.

Women's cooperatives are important in terms of evaluating women's labor. At the same time, within the framework of the principle of social responsibility, which is one of the basic principles of cooperatives, cooperative members contribute significantly to the sustainable development of the region in which they are located (Çetin, 2009).

While the rate of those who had knowledge about gastronomy tourism before the training was 26.3%, it was determined that this rate was 71.1% after the training. It was determined that the rate of those who had information about ecotourism before the training was 31.6% before the training, while it was approximately 79% after the training, and that the rate of those who had information about cooperatives was approximately 84% before the training and approximately 90% after the training (Table 4).

Table 4. Information on Gastronomy Tourism, Ecotourism and Cooperatives

	What is gastronomy?		What is ecotourism?		What is a cooperative?	
	Before Education	After Education	Before Education	After Education	Before Education	After Education
Yes	26.3	71.1	31.6	78.9	84.2	89.5
No	73.7	28.9	68.4	21.0	15.8	10.5
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Female producers were asked what problems they encountered most during olive cultivation. Approximately 23% of the producers stated that they had problems with diseases and pests, while 26.3% stated that they had problems in production due to drought. While 10.5% stated that they had difficulty finding workers, especially during the harvest period, 26.6% stated that diseases-pests, drought and labor supply were problems in production (Table 5).

Table 5. Problems Encountered During Olive Cultivation

Problems in olive production	%
Diseases	23.4
Drought	26.3
Problem finding workers	10.5
Drought-Problem finding workers	13.2
All of them	26.6

Women producers were given information about the factors affecting product quality in olive oil storage. While the rate of those who thought that storing olive oil in plastic bottles negatively affected the quality of olive oil before the training was approximately 74%, it was observed that it increased to 86.8% after the training. It was determined that the percentage of those who think that storing in glass bottles will negatively affect the quality decreased from approximately 11% to 7.9%. It is seen that the rate of those who think that storage in steel tanks negatively affects the quality of olive oil decreased from 15.8% to 5.3% (Table 6).

Table 6. Factors Affecting Product Quality in Olive Oil Storage

	Before	After
Bottle	73.7	86.8
Glass bottle	10.5	7.9
Stell tank	15.8	5.3

CONCLUSION

When we make a general evaluation of the research results; We understand that the education level of women living in rural areas is quite low, generally at primary school level, and that they actively contribute to every stage of both animal and plant production. It turns out that women living in rural areas are involved in every stage of agricultural production, both physically and spiritually, and although they also contribute economically, their contributions are invisible and they fall far behind their deserved place.

It is known that women living in rural areas are intensively involved in agricultural activities. Although all of the women participating in this study work intensively at every stage of olive production, approximately 58% of them see themselves as housewives.

Education plays an important role in eliminating regional imbalances. Increasing education has a multiplier effect not only on the labor market but also on the country's economy in the long term (Peker and Kubar, 2012). For this very reason, it is thought that it is important to increase the knowledge level of women producers by organizing training, especially in rural areas.

In this study, women producers participating in the study were given information about olive production and processing. Face-to-face interviews were held to determine the level of knowledge and changes in knowledge before and after the training. It is seen that there are significant increases in knowledge levels before and after the training.

If we need to make predictions about the next steps that can be taken; The first thing that comes to mind should be for farmer women in rural areas to be role models for girls and to strengthen the education of our women. Accordingly, with the increase in the literacy rate, the legalization of women's employment will be reflected in the provision of social security by encouraging women's entrepreneurship in rural areas and the workforce will be registered. These developments will enable women to progress rapidly in the process of becoming a cooperative. Women in rural areas should be supported to establish cooperatives or become members of cooperatives (Bozdoğan, 2023).

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